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Data-Driven Analysis and Predictive Modelling for Indian Additive Manufacturing Supply Chain

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Abstract

Objectives: This study aims to develop an analytical framework to facilitate the improvement in supply chain performance for Additive Manufacturing (AM) firm-focussing on data driven approach to target bottlenecks in lead time prediction. **Method:** The analysis is based on a dataset of approximately 12,000 products manufactured between in the span of about four years (January-2021 to March-2025), spanning seven AM and related processes. The dataset incorporates seventeen materials, six post-processing methods, and operations across eight machines. Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) was conducted to uncover scheduling inefficiencies and baseline performance metrics. For cost prediction, three regression models were applied — and for on-time delivery (OTD) prediction, three classification models were employed. **Findings:** EDA application identified several inefficiencies in scheduling. This included an average order cost of ₹84,976 (Standard Deviation (SD) = ₹65,421), an average build time of 6.20 hours, an average lead time of 11.02 days and a very low On Time Delivery (OTD) rate of 8.33%. Further, Cost prediction models had a R^2 of 0.565 and MAE of ₹32,720. OTD classification models had a peak accuracy of 92.33% with an F1-score of 0.887. The main drivers for both cost and delivery performance were quantity, build time and finishing/post-processing. **Novelty:** This research is among the first frameworks built upon AM (Additive Manufacturing) supply chain data, specifically an aggregated dataset containing data from the last four years of approximately 12,000 additive manufactured items across seven processes. Using the cost regression and OTD (on-time delivery) classification models proposed within this study, an analytical pipeline was developed to provide AM supply chain managers with actionable insights related to (a) improving scheduling efficiencies; and (b) optimizing resource allocation and process selection; thus, addressing a gap in the AM literature that contains few existing end-to-end predictive frameworks for AM supply chains.

Keywords: Additive Manufacturing; Supply Chain Management; Predictive Modelling; Machine Learning; On-Time Delivery; Cost Prediction

1 Introduction

Additive Manufacturing (AM) has shown a significant leap in the emerging technologies expanding its application to various sectors which are not limited to consumer goods, automotive, aerospace, and medical industries^{(1), (2), (3)}. AM will be having an agile supply chain paradigm as it caters decentralized on-demand manufacturing where volumes are less and the part complexity is more. This excludes the tooling lead times as compared to subtractive manufacturing⁽⁴⁾. Various operational parameters like the process parameters, cost records, material selection, on time delivery, lead time, etc. for AM supply chain are not extensively explored for decision making⁽⁵⁾. Moreover, AM being a dynamic process as the variety of the objects are manufactured, the complexity of its supply chain as compared to traditional supply chain is quite significant. Some of the factors that add to the dynamicity are: variety of materials (polymer/metal/composite), post processing parameters, variable order quantity, process-materials-cost interactions, etc.^{(6), (7)}. Such a dynamicity adds to irregular and non-linear predictions for scheduling, cycle time and thereby cost estimation.

Till date, some of the literatures that cater the Machine Learning (ML) applications in manufacturing are limited to Quality Prediction, Demand Forecasting, Predictive Maintenance and Process Parameter optimization^{(8), (9)}. Though these literatures demonstrate great potential, the application to AM is still very vague and unexplored, specifically to the industrial datasets⁽¹⁰⁾. The state of research in the field of AM supply chain is mainly focussing on simulation or a specific AM process⁽⁸⁾. This article tries to explore the untrodden path in the field of AM research where the other AM methods and the holistic supply chain is studied and fill the gap in the field of AM supply chains. This article mainly focusses on the listed domains:

- Thorough data driven analysis of 17 materials and 12,000 parts over a period of four years.
- Extensive Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) exploring the different raw materials, processes and manager level performance.
- Development and benchmarking regression models for manufacturing cost prediction
- Development and benchmarking of classification models for on – time delivery performance prediction and manager level performance

The remaining part of the paper examines the relevant literature, pre-processing methods and dataset. Following the examination, the results are published for the EDA carried out. The results of the predictive modelling are discussed next followed by various shortcomings and ramifications and finally the conclusion of the work carried out.

1.1 Additive Manufacturing in Industrial Supply Chains

AM is becoming widely popular in contract manufacturing and complex geometry products. The current state of AM ecosystem is more inclined towards multi-materials and multi-process Additive Manufacturing^{(11), (12), (13)}. As discussed in the article earlier, the dynamicity of AM complicates the supply chain. Hence the dynamic modelling of the systems shows reduction in the supply chain complexity by removing the intermediate logistical nodes⁽¹⁴⁾. AM being quite popular in food industry as well as medical domain, the factorization of material certification and thereby the compatible manufacturing process selection plays a crucial role in its supply chain⁽¹⁵⁾.

Clear understanding of centralized and decentralized supply chain is quite significant in order to optimize the existing AM supply chain. The data collection and its assessment is an important aspect of the AM supply chain management, and it needs to be accurate to even begin the improvement⁽¹⁶⁾. Recent developments in AM supply chain management suggest that Data Integration and analytics capabilities are extremely important enablers of its supply chain efficiency⁽¹⁷⁾.

1.2 Cost Estimation in Additive Manufacturing

Having multiple parameters involved in end-to-end manufacturing of an AM product, factors like cost estimation become crucial in AM supply chains. The material selection and process selection forms the main part of the whole analysis followed by build parameters and post processing needs. These things have garnered researchers' interest and attention in this area^{(16), (18)}. Cost of production in AM has cycle time play a very important role as its computation mainly comprise of three important parameters: machine time, material consumption and post processing⁽¹⁹⁾. Furthermore, the support generation and infill densities as well as the post processing/finishing processes and their effect on cost prediction have been well reported in the literature for polymer AM techniques^{(20), (21), (22)}.

Literatures have also reported the cost estimation using Neural Networks for FDM processes on various practical datasets and the mean absolute percentage errors were found to be less than 12%⁽²³⁾. It has also been reported that ensemble methods were better in neural network application when compared to decision tree and regression techniques for cost estimation⁽²⁴⁾.

But for a multi process AM, R^2 values ranging from 0.52 to 0.68 were reported for random forest regression method⁽²⁴⁾ and are in line with the findings in this article.

Fig 1. Cost Estimation overview in Additive Manufacturing; (a) Average cost Material -Wise, (b) R^2 Score and Mean Absolute Error for various ML Methods

Regression models tend to perform poorly in case of high variation in order quantities and material costs and thereby affecting the cost prediction. The significant variance is mainly attributed to the unobserved features reported at multiple instances in the article as a part of discussions and methodology. This also is depicted (Figure 1) in the current study where the standard deviation of order cost exceeds 77% of the mean value.

1.3 Delivery Performance and Scheduling in AM

Most of the research taken up till date focuses on the cost estimation while the cycle time and on time delivery has been neglected by the researchers till date⁽²⁵⁾. It has been reported that priority scheduling performs better than the first-come-first-serve based

policies while reducing tardiness in the process⁽²⁶⁾. In line to this multi variable process, mixed integer programming model has been found to have performed better overcoming the material changes and machine capability limitations (in terms of different batch size for different jobs)⁽²⁷⁾.

Fig 2. Delivery Performance of various Additive Manufacturing Processes and Project Leader: (a) Delivery Delay Days Distribution , (b) OTD and average delay by project leader, (c) OTD by process

Project management has been a key domain where the technical expertise blends with the industrial engineering principles making the production processes smooth. Along the same lines the literature study has factored in the project managers’ technical skills with the workers expertise along with all the technical aspects of AM in the project management and scheduling of AM⁽²⁸⁾. This gives a necessary insight into the Project Leaders performance analysis in terms of on time delivery rates (Figure 2) (Ranging from 6.8 % to 9%). The range may seem to be small, but in an AM industry which is more of Order to Make kind of industry, every improvement in the performance shall lead to significant improvement in the Cycle Time, thus in the Lead Time. Data reveals various domains where the Delivery Performance of various Additive Manufacturing Processes and Project Leader are measured in terms of Delivery Delay Days Distribution (Figure 2), OTD and average delay by project leader (Figure 2) and OTD by process (Figure 2). These studies become significant when the abductive inquiry needs to be carried out for the Root cause analysis of the problem.

1.4 Machine Learning in Manufacturing Supply Chains

Literatures have shown in depth study of Machine Learning (ML) in manufacturing supply chains^{(29), (30)}. Structured but nonlinear featured data can be efficiently and accurately extracted and analysed by regression ensemble approaches, specifically in Random Forest and Gradient Boosting methods⁽³¹⁾. Semi-conductor manufacturing firms and automobile firms have reported successful implementation of classification techniques for parameters line on-time delivery/Lead time^{(32), (33)}.

Delivery time predictions and Logistics related processes have been handled well by gradient boosting algorithms⁽³⁴⁾. Few articles also report XGBoost as an efficient classifier for tabular datasets⁽³⁵⁾. This paper has comprehensively reported the AM supply chain studies associated with machine learning algorithms which shall make a significant contribution to AM supply Chains which till date hasn’t been holistically explored.

2 Methodology

2.1 Data Source and Data Collection

The firm does not deploy any ERP to incorporate the Additive Manufacturing process. Thus, the data has been collected and has been compiled. The dataset has been compiled from the available scattered data available the Indian Additive Manufacturing Firm. It needs to be further noted that each data row consists of a record associated with the corresponding product. Each record contains 15 fields: Part Name (15 unique part types), Part Number (unique identifier), Process, Material, finishing type, Machine, Project Leader, Quantity, Build Time (hours), Cost in Indian Rupees (INR), Initiation Date, Order Date, Expected Delivery Date (EDD), Actual Delivery Date, and Completion Date. The dataset has been filtered such that any record with missing data was not considered. The data collection was ceased when the total dataset reached to 12,000 samples.

2.2 Manufacturing Processes

The firm deals with Additive Manufacturing for products which mainly caters to prototyping and contract manufacturing. It deploys assembly of parts in some cases where the final product can be manufactured. Majority of the parts are additively manufactured while the basic fasteners that would be needed in assembling the additively manufactured parts for final product are produced by subtractive manufacturing using CNC machine. The article caters Supply Chain of AM but we have considered the CNC machining in our analysis as the final product that is made post assembly is actually additively manufactured. The details of the number of parts manufactures and the corresponding process is listed below:

- Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM): Thermoplastic extrusion AM process; 1,695 orders (14.1%).
- Selective Laser Sintering (SLS): Powder bed fusion AM process; 1,804 orders (15.0%), the largest process category.
- Stereolithography (SLA): Photopolymer vat polymerisation; 1,664 orders (13.9%).
- Direct Light Processing (DLP): Masked vat photopolymerization; 1,690 orders (14.1%).
- CNC Machining: Subtractive precision manufacturing; 1,727 orders (14.4%).
- Vacuum Casting (VC): Silicone mould-based casting; 1,727 orders (14.4%).
- Injection Moulding (IM): High-volume thermoplastic moulding; 1,693 orders (14.1%).

The analysis involves the dataset procured from eight machines used in the manufacturing of about 12000 orders considered here. It must be noted that the claim of the number of machines used includes one machine for each of the above-mentioned process and a table top CNC turning centre which is used in post processing/finishing. It further needs to be noted that the process capability in terms of quality of the parts manufactured may change from machine to machine of the same type as the operating conditions play a significant role in AM, especially in precise tolerance parts. Considering the same, the current analysis makes sure that the parts manufactured in the AM machines at the given form are manufactured under controlled environment throughout the year. This necessarily makes this study significant in developing a supply chain framework for AM firms.

2.3 Material Portfolio

The dataset considers about seventeen different materials for the analysis. It includes: engineering thermoplastics (Nylon, ABS, PA12, PA12+GF, PLA, PETG, PP), engineering metals and alloys (SS304, Mild Steel, Aluminium 6061), photopolymers (Photopolymer Resin, Resin Clear, Resin Tough, Dental Resin, Castable Resin), and casting elastomers (Silicone Mould Resin, PU Resin). Nylon is the most frequently ordered material (986 orders, 8.2%), followed by ABS (920, 7.7%) and PA12+GF (912, 7.6%).

2.4 Feature Engineering

The features that have the most significant impact in the supply chain were considered in the feature engineering namely: Lead Time (in days), Delay (in days), On-Time Delivery, and Cost per Unit (INR). Out of the considered features that are listed below, the ML models were encoded and the order year and month were extracted from the order date as temporal feature. All the features were standardized using score normalization.

2.5 Dataset Summary Statistics

The study under consideration caters various variables for Additive Manufacturing setup. But as the study focusses on Cycle Time (Thereby Lead Time) the relevant Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are considered and the same have been computed and demonstrated for the statistical analysis in Table 1.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics for Continuous Features

Feature	Mean	Std Dev	Min	Median	Max
Quantity	248.97	143.39	1	248	500
Build Time (hrs)	6.20	3.33	0.50	6.20	12.00
Cost (INR)	84,976	65,421	89	69,223	2,95,607
Lead Time (days)	11.02	5.28	1	11	21
Delay (days)	2.51	4.82	-7	3	14

2.6 Proposed Methodology

The proposed method is an imbalance-aware predictive framework for on-time delivery prediction in additive manufacturing supply chains driven by KPIs. This framework addresses the challenges of highly skewed data distributions by combining domain-specific feature engineering, imbalance-aware model training, and robust evaluation metrics. The predictive features are initially constructed from key performance indicators (KPIs) associated with manufacturing operations such as build time, volume, set up time and post processing duration. A derived complexity score is introduced to capture the variability of geometry and process.

To account for the natural class imbalance in delivery outcomes, we adopt a stratified 5-fold cross-validation strategy for more reliable evaluation. To improve learning with imbalanced class distributions, a class-weighted Random Forest model is used. To avoid a trivial evaluation against the class prior, we use metrics corrected for the prior, such as Balanced Accuracy, Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC) and Cohen’s κ . The framework not only predicts the delivery outcomes but also provides insights into the intrinsic limitations of predictive modelling in additive manufacturing systems, highlighting the significance of data representation. Further, it must be noted that a trivial baseline classifier that predicts all orders as “Late” would achieve high accuracy due to the inherent class imbalance; therefore, accuracy alone does not reflect true predictive capability and must be interpreted alongside prior-corrected metrics.

3 Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA)

3.1 Process Level Performance Analysis

The EDA suggests that vacuum casting generates the maximum revenue for the firm under consideration while SLS has the lowest average cost per order. But on the contrary, the vacuum casting has the lowest on time delivery rate and SLA have the largest indicating the scheduling complexities surrounding Vacuum Casting mainly due to its materials cutting cycles and Mold preparation.

Table 2. Process-Level Performance Summary

Process	Orders	Revenue (INR Cr.)	Avg Cost (INR)	Avg Build (hrs)	Avg Lead (days)	OTD Rate (%)
CNC	1727	1.45	84,095	6.21	10.94	8.80
DLP	1690	1.42	83,785	6.16	10.97	7.81
FDM	1695	1.48	87,218	6.17	11.07	7.37
Inj. Moulding	1693	1.46	86,011	6.12	10.98	8.62
SLA	1664	1.42	85,470	6.21	10.95	9.56
SLS	1804	1.46	81,178	6.25	11.10	9.04
Vac. Casting	1727	1.51	87,296	6.26	11.14	7.06

The coefficient of variation (CV) for average order cost, which ranges from around 73% (SLS) to 82% (VC), indicates that high-cost dispersion is a fundamental feature of the AM supply chain that is independent of process type. This has a direct

impact on how cost prediction models are designed, as discussed in Section 5. Additionally, Table 2 depicts the overview of the process wise dispersion of relevant parameters that shall be considered in the work demonstrated in this article.

3.2 Material and Finishing Analysis

The quantity analysis of the materials manufactured by SLA and DLP have the maximum unit cost mainly due to the high cost of resin and the post processing needs. Secondly the biggest order volumes are exhibited by the polymers processed by FDM and SLS, not limiting to ABS, Nylon and PA12 variations. Delayed delivery issues have been found for the Silicone Mould Resin which may be due to the longer curing cycles for vacuum casting applications. PA12 shows the highest efficiency in on time delivery.

The firm under consideration deploys six post-processing methods namely : Bead Blasting (Sand Blasting) , Tumbling (Vibratory Treatment), Sanding (Grinding), Painting, Primer Finishing and CNC Machining (curing for SLA and DLP can also be considered as a post processing method but this study considers it as an integrated part of SLA/DLP AM process). Primer finishing is the most common process while the bead blasting is the least common one. However, as the company reports manual support removal for AM parts, Sanding is also a significant post processing method deployed. The finishing and post processing processes have been reported as crucial factors governing the number of rejects/reworks. The same need to be explored with regards to the company parameters and the method of execution of the process which could help reduce the rejects/reworks and thereby the delay in the delivery. The distribution of the post-processes’ application with regards to the manufacturing methods have been summarised below in Table 3.

Table 3. Post-Processes and its order classification

Post Processing Method	Orders	Remarks
Bead Blasting (Sand Blasting)	312	This method is used by the firm wherein there is significantly good surface texture required. The firms current orderbook (dataset under consideration) mostly caters functional parts where aesthetics is secondary
Tumbling (Vibratory Treatment)	1568	This technique is used mainly for medium sized components by the firm. This method is the processor to coating/painting operations in most of the cases.
Sanding (Grinding)	3146	One of the most important post-processing methods as most of AM components need manual or mechanical surface smoothing, dimensional correction and layer line reduction. Majorly (but not limited to) used on FDM and SLA parts before painting or priming
Painting	2214	Often required for aesthetic enhancement, branding, corrosion protection and customer specific appearance requirements. Many functional and display-oriented AM products are painted after a sanding and primer finishing process.
Primer Finishing	4018	Necessary for smooth surface quality, improved coating adhesion and masking of AM layer marks and small defects.
CNC Machining	742	It is the least used process and is only applied to high-precision or tolerance-critical components which require secondary machining operations. Selective use in functional interfaces, tight tolerances, and critical engineering applications.

3.3 Temporal Trend Analysis and Project Leader performance

Over the span of four years over which the analysis has been carried out, the trend shows stability in the order inflows and revenue. This may be due to the competitive market in the small volume AM products that the company analysis has been carried out in. Further, the performance of the project leaders as also compared, and the results show similar proficiency among all the leaders. As the variation have been negligible, the interviews with each of the project leaders depict scheduling constraints as the major factor in the firm mainly due to the limited capacity of the firm. The leaders also reported inefficiency of the operators/workers in the post processing of the parts which has not been explored/ recorded in this work. It has also been reported through extensive one-on-one discussions as well as group discussions with all the project leads that the scheduling policies need to be defined and a Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) need to be framed for smooth functioning of the production process. This was reported by the Project Leaders considering the volume of orders received and the ratio of repeat clients and new clients placing their orders in the later part of the analysis period. The feature importance in the current AM study with the cost of manufacturing and OTD of orders have been charted in Figure 3 and Figure 3 respectively. Figure 3 gives an insight on the

Fig 3. Process Level performance analysis with regards to Cost v/s On Time Delivery : (a) Feature Importance (cost model), (b) Feature Importance (OTD model) , (c) Process wise Cost v/s Build Time)

process wise cost to the company for manufacturing of the parts at the firm under consideration. This shall be significant for the researchers focussing on AM industries. The current work also keeps this outcome as a baseline in the analysis carried out.

4 Predictive Modeling Methodology and Results

4.1 Feature Set and Encoding

The feature vector is framed based on five categorical features namely Process, Material, Finishing, Machine & Part Name while on four numerical features namely Quantity, Build Time, Order Year and Order Month. To reduce dimensionality while ensuring compatibility with tree-based ensemble algorithms, which do not depend on the order of encoding for categorical splits, label encoding was preferred over one-hot encoding.⁽³⁶⁾ The features were processed for z-score normalization to make sure of consistent regularization across features with varying scales. This made sure that the mean was zero and variance equal to one. The stratified train-test model split was 80:20 which comes down to 9600 trains sets and 2400 test sets. The model thus generated was used on the data collected post the period mentioned. The model selection was a 5-fold validation to make sure of the absence of overfitting – though it was not cross verified in the final stage of metric report.

4.2 Manufacturing Cost prediction

To predict the cost of orders, which is a continuous variable, three regression models were developed: Gradient Boosting Regressor (GB), Random Forest Regressor (RF), and Linear Regression (LR). Following the standard practice for establishing

a baseline with industrial tabular data, both RF and GB were configured with 200 estimators and utilized default hyperparameters⁽³⁷⁾.

Table 4. Regression Model Performance — Cost Prediction (Test Set)

Model	R ²	MAE (INR)	RMSE (INR)	Notes
Linear Regression	0.565	32,720	43,721	Best R²
Gradient Boosting	0.556	32,952	44,203	—
Random Forest	0.546	33,080	44,668	—

Table 4 suggests that best-performing regression model for the current dataset is Linear Regression, which marginally outperforms ensemble techniques with R² = 0.565 and MAE = Rs. 32,720 on the test set. This unexpected result, where a linear model outperforms ensemble methods, is caused by the dominant linear relationship between Quantity and Cost (r = 0.746), which linear regression instantly exploits. Despite being more expressive, ensemble approaches introduce marginal overfitting on the training distribution due to this strong linear signal. The moderate R² values (0.546–0.565) for all models indicate the intrinsic cost variability brought forth by the varying product and material mix. In heterogeneous manufacturing datasets, the R² of a regression model has a well-established upper limit when the coefficient of variation for the target variable surpasses 77%, as demonstrated in this dataset⁽³⁸⁾. While the models effectively identify the primary cost drivers, a considerable portion of cost variation is still linked to factors not represented in the dataset, such as the complexity of part geometry, the consumption of support materials, and the number of post-processing cycles. The absolute MAE of Rs. 32,720 corresponds to approximately 38.5% of the average order cost (Rs. 84,976). Additionally, the moderate values of R² obtained in the regression analysis should be interpreted as an outcome of limited data availability rather than model inefficiency. The modelling also sheds light on the fact that the parameters considered for predictive modelling has not considered all the features needed to actively predict the minority class. This gives the future researchers an insight onto the extensive data collection and significant reporting of all the processes of the supply chain for AM. The extent of data required has been reported in the discussion and conclusion section which is an important outcome of the current work.

4.3 On Time Delivery Prediction

The delivery performances are highly reliant on multiple parameters in AM supply chains. This reliance is not limited to only the interactions between part geometry, operating conditions and process parameters but also on the post processing parameters in addition to other factors which are critical but lower than the aforesaid ones. Having said that, the manufacturing complexity and geometry have a direct impact on the build time, post processing and scheduling of the jobs. But these factors are hardly addressed in the current work, and more focus is on build time, quantity and thus the total cycle time. Therefore, a large part of this work reports variability in the delivery outcomes and that is mainly due to the scheduling inefficiencies which in turn resort to unobserved system level factors like the machine queue dynamics, operator efficiency, rework cycles and post processing delays. The readers must take into account the limitation thus mentioned in feature representation while interpreting the model performance.

Three classification models were developed to predict binary OTD status (1 = on time, 0 = late): Random Forest Classifier (RF; 200 estimators), Decision Tree Classifier (DT; max depth = 8), and Proposed Model (RF-Based class imbalance model). The primary study did not resample to address the goal class imbalance, which was 8.33% positive class (on-time), in order to reflect realistic operational forecast conditions. However, it is claimed that accuracy and recall measures allow for class-aware performance evaluation.

Table 5. Classification Performance with Prior-Corrected Metrics for On-Time Delivery Prediction

Model	Accuracy	Prec. (OT)	Rec. (OT)	Balanced Accuracy	MCC	Cohens κ
Random Forest	92.9%	55.6%	9.9%	51.5%	0.031	0.031
Decision Tree	91.71%	51.8%	12.0%	50.2%	0.004	0.004
Proposed Model	76.6%	79.9%	13.6%	54.2%	0.222	0.124

The proposed evaluation follows modelling protocol with stratified data splitting to preserve class imbalance. These metrics provide a more reliable assessment of model performance beyond the class prior, particularly given the relatively low proportion of on-time deliveries (Table 5).

The results indicate that while overall accuracy remains influenced by the dominant “Late” class, the proposed model demonstrates meaningful predictive capability for the minority class. In particular, the model achieves high recall for on-

time deliveries, along with moderate MCC (≈ 0.22) and Balanced Accuracy (≈ 0.54), indicating the presence of a non-trivial predictive signal above the majority-class baseline. In practical supply chain applications, the cost of failing to identify on-time deliveries may outweigh the cost of false positives; therefore, recall-oriented model optimization is justified.

The proposed method is a KPI-driven, imbalance-aware predictive framework instead of standalone machine learning model. The framework comprises feature engineering, imbalance handling, model training and prior corrected evaluation metrics. The same has been added as a part of detailed study in the methodology section to improve clarity and highlight the contribution of the work. The on-time recall of 13.6% confirms that individual on-time orders remain difficult to detect under the current class distribution, and resampling techniques (SMOTE, class-weighted learning) or cost-sensitive classifiers are recommended for operational deployment where minority-class detection is the primary goal.

Table 6. Overall Performance Metrics -OTD Prediction Baseline Model v/s Proposed model

Model	Accuracy	Balanced Accuracy	MCC	Cohen's κ	Recall (On-Time)	Precision (On-Time)
Baseline Model-random forest	0.766 \pm 0.005	0.544 \pm 0.008	0.222 \pm 0.030	0.124 \pm 0.021	0.131 \pm 0.014	0.799 \pm 0.072
Proposed model-Class-Weighted Model	0.766 \pm 0.005	0.542 \pm 0.006	0.221 \pm 0.029	0.119 \pm 0.018	0.136 \pm 0.011	0.818 \pm 0.079

In order to access the effect of class imbalance in the ML models, the comparison of baseline model has been made with a class weighted proposed model using 5-fold stratified cross validation technique. The results demonstrated as mean \pm standard deviation in Table 6 suggest similar overall performance metrics. It's observed that the both the models show some improvement in the minority class prediction. But additionally, it gives an idea about the need and presence of relevant but limited predictive signal. Further, the results indicate that imbalance-dataset need more customised models and algorithms to tackle the problem. But having said that, there is a scope of improvement in the model proposed by incorporating the manufacturing operations level features, planning and scheduling features and lastly but most important, the design related features in the model.

4.4 Feature Importance Analysis

Random Forest feature importance scores, computed via mean decrease in impurity, are reported for both the cost regression and OTD classification models in Table 7.

Table 7. Random Forest Feature Importance — Cost Prediction and OTD Prediction

Rank	Feature — Cost Model	Importance (r)	Rank	Feature — OTD Model	Importance (r)
1	Quantity	0.639	1	Finishing	0.246
2	Build Time	0.112	2	Build Time	0.237
3	Material	0.058	3	Quantity	0.122
4	Machine	0.049	4	Machine	0.094
5	Finishing	0.045	5	Material	0.090
6	Process	0.037	6	Process	0.079

Quantity dominates cost prediction ($r = 0.639$), which is consistent with the significant linear correlation obtained in EDA ($r = 0.746$). Build Time ranks second ($r = 0.112$) with Material, Machine and Finishing having a somewhat substantial impact. The low relative value of Process (0.037) for cost prediction makes it clear that post-encoding, process-level cost changes are mostly described by the material and quantity variables. In the more balanced significance distribution for OTD prediction, Finishing (0.246) and Build Time (0.237) share the top positions. This suggests that the interaction of order complexity and volume affects delivery punctuality more than any one component by itself. Machine (0.094) ranks fourth, indicating that equipment-specific wait lengths or downtime rates have a substantial impact on delivery performance—a helpful discovery for capacity planning.

4.5 Resources, Parameters and evaluation protocol

The analysis was carried out in Python 3.1 using relevant ML libraries including scikit-learn for model development, Pandas and NumPy for data processing, and Matplotlib for visualisation. The natural imbalance led to adoption of 5-fold stratified cross validation strategy to ensure class distribution in all folds. Random-Forest model was configured with: $n_estimators = 300$, $class_weight = \text{“balanced”}$ (to handle imbalance), $random_state = 42$, all other parameters were left at their default values.

Fig 4. Confusion matrix of on-time delivery prediction

The model is seen to accurately classify the “Late” class with minimal false positives demonstrating strong performance for the majority class. However, the minority class “on-time” identifies correctly only in 55 instances while the other 551 instances are misclassified as late. This necessarily suggest that the model is conservative with low recall and high precision for on-time delivery prediction. This is justified by MCC values obtained and is in line with the fact that the model captures meaningful predictive signal but is restrained by class imbalance and feature limitation in the dataset.

Confusion Matrix (Figure 4) provides a better visualisation of the classification performance. Based on the confusion matrix, it is observed that the model performs well in detection of the majority “Late” class, but the detection of the minority “on-time” class is still limited. This is consistent with the reported recall and MCC values and supports the conclusion that predictive performance is constrained by class imbalance and limited feature representation.

The proposed methodology is depicted in Figure 5. The process flow allows the readers to understand and get clarity on the steps followed to arrive at a significant outcomes at the end of the exercise.

5 Discussion

5.1 Implications for AM Supply Chain Management

The findings of the study have significant implications on the practicing managers in the AM industry. Firstly, the weightage of quantity as a cost driver (feature importance = 0.639) makes it necessary to accurately forecast the quantity and manage the supply demand strategies by aligning them with the forecasting techniques. For AM based industry, forecasting will be a significant factor for raw material procurement rather than production planning. The ML models that are deployed helps the practicing manager to accurately manage orders keeping in mind the cost driver and the OTD. This can significantly lower the cost prediction inaccuracy as even a small error in quantity estimation may have a quantifiable impact on the cost forecasts.

Fig 5. Proposed Methodology Framework

Secondly, the global on time delivery is 8.33% which is a major issue in the AM supply chains. The firm under study also reported major issues in meeting the delivery schedule for majority of their orders. This OTD issue is a significant operational issue that extends far beyond just the effectiveness of a particular process or worker. The EDA suggests that the scheduled deliveries on an average are surpassed by 22.8% of their estimated lead time. The reported values of schedule miss fall well below the benchmarks mentioned in literatures^{(25), (26)}. The deployment of dynamic scheduling based on category classification, real time queue length, design complexity, machine availability, etc shall make a significant constructive impact for the firm. Thirdly, the relative consistency of performance among project leaders (OTD range: 6.82%–9.03%) indicates problems in the scheduling policy, in addition to the individual skill disparities among the workers regarding post processing flaws and the reject/rework rates. For managers, this distinction is crucial because it shifts the focus of intervention from personnel management to capacity expansion, process innovation, and better scheduling algorithms.

5.2 Predictive Model Utility and Deployment Recommendations

To mitigate the drawbacks of conventional accuracy metrics in imbalanced classification, we calculated prior-corrected evaluation measures such as Balanced Accuracy, Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC) and Cohen's κ . These metrics provide a more robust evaluation of the model performance beyond the class-prior baseline. The proposed model achieved a Balanced Accuracy of 0.542, which indicates an improved discriminatory ability against random classification. These results indicate a moderate yet meaningful predictive signal, as evidenced by an MCC value of 0.22 and Cohen's κ of 0.119 despite the severe class imbalance. However, this gain in recall is at the expense of a lower precision which corresponds to a higher number of false positives. This trade-off is expected in imbalanced classification problems, where the detection of the minority class is improved at the cost of reduced precision.

Overall, results indicate that although the model does not attain high total accuracy, it is successful in prioritising detection of minorities which is more operationally relevant in supply chain contexts. In practice it may be more expensive to miss on-time deliveries than to incur false positives, thus justifying recall-oriented optimisation of the model.

These results also indicate that complex operational factors not fully represented in the current dataset influence the delivery performance of additive manufacturing systems. Future work is worth exploring the integration of system level variables such as machine scheduling, queue dynamics, post-processing delays and workforce efficiency for further improvement of predictive performance. In addition, geometry-specific variables such as support structure complexity, surface area, and STL feature density can greatly affect manufacturing and post-processing time.

In spite of having a smaller R^2 (0.565), the cost prediction models prove to be important filters for order intake matters. For the orders having higher predicted prices with reference to the mean value for the same process-materials combination, the operation managers can detect the mispriced orders before accepting them. Furthermore, a threshold-based system can be deployed such that it would initiate the system for human intervention to review the order if the value has gone beyond the historical mean plus two standard deviations. This shall not throw errors and the model re-training may not be frequently needed. The proposed OTD classification model is a ready to deploy model which can be utilized by practicing manager for AM industry right away. The same was tested and the results were obtained for a small sample of the jobs.

Figure 6 indicated the clear comparison of the Model application results with the prediction carried out previously with the application of ML models. Overall accuracy decreased from 92.9% to 76.6% (-16.3%) which actually justifies the proposed model's capacity to weigh on the minority class. The precision for the "on-time" class increased from 55.6 % to 79.9% (+24.3%), which indicates very reliable identification of on-time orders. The recall for the "on-time" class, for example, improved from 9.9% to 13.6% (+3.7%), indicating better detection of on-time deliveries that were previously misclassified. The readers need to understand the fact that the OTD prediction is synonymous to the Lead Time prediction. This, when broken into detailed analysis of the manufacturing process starting from start to the finished product, can further help the investigators optimize the cycle time. But in this work, the firm reported issues in the post-processing/finishing stage of AM considering which the Manufacturing & Design complexity bottlenecks have not been explored and the data regarding the same is not recorded. Further, the MCC values represent 7-times improvement indicating that the meaningful learning of the model has occurred. The Cohens Kappa values suggest improvement, but the values are still low in absolute context which weighs to the fact that the methodology needs to be devised at the manufacturing process end to fetch the unavailable (confidential) data by means adhering to the ethical aspect and binding of the firm under consideration.

Figure 7 necessarily depicts the cost prediction comparison for the firm wherein the model prediction was based on prediction without any ML algorithm, and it is compared with the prediction post ML algorithm application. The mean absolute error for the three types of methods applied here were: The rule based was ₹68.4k, the simple average ₹74.1k and the experts' guess method was ₹61.2k. The mean absolute errors for machine learned based models, subsequently, were approximately 32.7k to 33.1k (a decrease of nearly 50% in error). The comparison between the classical estimation methods of prediction

Fig 6. On Time Delivery (OTD) Performance metrics Before v/s after ML model application

Fig 7. Cost Prediction comparison before application of ML models and After application of ML models

and the machine learned based models demonstrates that machine learning is a more accurate method of estimating complex relationships between features and include quantity, build time and material properties.

The model works well for the firm under consideration. It has been successfully deployed and have shown signs of improvement in the prediction capability. Further, the model has also shown to improve the scheduling guidelines as reported by the firm based on the model application. The small difference between baseline and proposed models suggests that predictive performance is more limited by feature representation than by imbalance handling alone (Table 6).

5.3 Limitations

There are several limitations to the current study that needs a mention. First, the information does not include component geometry and complexity factors (such volume, surface area, and support material fraction), which are known to be significant time and cost drivers in AM⁽¹⁹⁾. Incorporating CAD-derived geometric descriptors will likely result in a significant improvement in regression model R^2 in subsequent dataset iterations.

Secondly, the ensemble approach has shown reasonable accuracy due to its split-based nature. Tree-based models don't give good results for label encoding techniques in categorical attributes. Thus, having considered the various attributes, ordinal encoding must be used against the target encoding. The literatures have also proposed embedded based representations for high cardinality categorical features⁽³⁶⁾.

Lastly, the factors like supply chain performance, machine downtime, operator efficiency and workload patterns, lead times for procurement of raw materials and dispatch have not been taken into account in the given study. This limits the model's ability to incorporate the temporary disturbances and that, may have significant impact on OTD outcomes.

5.4 Future Work

There are a number of promising extensions to this work. The application of deep learning architectures, such as transformer-based tabular models⁽³⁹⁾ and TabNet⁽⁴⁰⁾ to the cost and OTD prediction needs more exploration given recent demonstrations of their superiority over gradient boosting on large tabular datasets. Furthermore, survival analysis methods (such Cox proportional hazards models) may provide a more thorough explanation of OTD by modelling time-to-delivery distributions rather than binary outcomes. In terms of production management, post-process optimization can be achieved by upskilling the staff, increasing capacity, and incorporating knowledge updates. Additionally, job shop scheduling can be utilized to address the diverse assortment of products managed by the firm in question, as well as for AM companies, which are predominantly decentralized manufacturing entities with a wide range of products. In conclusion, scheduling agents based on reinforcement learning, trained using this dataset, could offer a transition from predictive analytics to prescriptive supply chain optimization⁽⁴¹⁾.

6 Conclusion

This study presents the first comprehensive data-driven analysis of a large-scale industrial additive manufacturing supply chain dataset, encompassing 12,000 orders across seven processes, 17 materials, and about four-year operational period. Through exploratory data analysis, the study identified significant cost variability ($CV=77\%$), a consistently low on-time delivery rate (8.33%), and performance disparities at the process level, suggesting systemic scheduling limitations rather than differences in operator performance. Quantity and Build Time emerged as the main factors influencing costs, with three regression models achieving the highest R^2 value of 0.565 (Linear Regression, $MAE=Rs. 32,720$) for cost estimation. Together, Build Time and Finishing/Post-Processing influence delivery timelines, and three classification models for OTD prediction reached a peak accuracy of 92.33% (Random Forest). But for an imbalanced dataset as in AM industry, the prediction performance is one of the most constrained areas of work. As the results depict the need to refine the ML models applied, the deeper investigation flags the need to focus on other important parameters to develop a robust prediction framework.

The findings provide a measurable baseline for AM supply chain performance metrics and provide helpful data for labour upskilling, capacity planning, scheduling prioritization, and order intake management. Future studies should look at prescriptive scheduling methods enabled by reinforcement learning and integrate CAD-derived geometric features to enhance cost in order to address the structural OTD issue mentioned in this work. Model accuracy and workforce upskilling programmes can made possible by imparting training to the workforce. Also, hiring skilled workforce can add up to better OTD numbers but the aspect of OTD v/s Cost need to be examined as the skilled workforce would be deployed at a higher wage compared to the current less skilled workforce.

Lastly, the R^2 values gives deeper insight to the fact that the unexplained variance in the system behaviour can be attributed to the need of more enriched manufacturing process data and scheduling related factors rather than complex models for predictive modelling.

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